

Digital Marketing in Enhancing the Commercial Value of Natural Frond Crafts

Oterlo Seropi ^{1*}

¹ Stanford University, United States

ABSTRACT

The study aims to promote products made by artisans who use natural fibers within the community. The analysis of the business canvas model revealed that the primary challenge encountered by craftspeople was the difficulty in establishing direct access to consumers. Consequently, artists receive diverse training to effectively market products and reach consumers by utilizing digital marketing via social media platforms (Facebook and Instagram) and business website development. The training empowers them to market handcrafted products to both local and national clients. Through digital marketing, they can extend their reach to promote their products internationally

Keywords: Consumer Access; Business Canvas Model; Social Media

INTRODUCTION

The village's handcraft enterprise utilizing natural fibers has undergone substantial growth. Since its establishment in 2023, the artisan group, which originally comprised 2 individuals, currently supports 40 families. Similarly, the sales turnover of craftsmen, valued at 56,800,000 in 2023, has escalated to 1,148,000,000 annually in 2024 (Murtigading, 2021). Initially, they focused on crafting decorative items for rooms, including tissue boxes, light boxes, and photo figures; however, their manufacturing has since broadened to encompass waste baskets, furniture composed of mixed materials, and wall adornments. Craft groups exist to address the challenges faced by artisans, facilitating skill enhancement, promoting knowledge exchange, and reinforcing their market position with producers of raw materials and craft purchasers. The distinctive attributes of natural handicrafts render products crafted from natural fibers highly favored by urban populations for residential, commercial, and

Received: 2023-06-09 Revised: 2023-06-21 Accepted: 2023-09-21 Published: 2023-12-31

hospitality requirements (Rejeb et al., 2020). Currently, public awareness about natural products is very popular so that the need for handicrafts made from natural materials has increased. Likewise, commercial buildings such as business offices and hotels urgently need natural handicrafts to improve the company's image as an environmentally friendly meeting place. The metropolitan community is well-informed about green products.

Those who pay attention to the orientation of environmental sustainability also support the selection of household appliances made from natural materials. The constraints faced by the artisan group, which utilizes natural fibers, necessitate a substantial resolution to enhance their bargaining position with buyers. Enthusiasts of natural products predominantly comprise individuals and hotels in metropolitan areas. A limited portion of artisan products has successfully penetrated international markets, including Australia, Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines, and several European nations such as the United Kingdom and the Netherlands (Matakaca, 2020). Intermediaries or resellers mediate artisan access to consumers, and the order intensity from these intermediaries significantly influences production quantities.

The ability to promote products makes the profit obtained by intermediaries very high, which is 100% to 150%, far from the profit enjoyed by artisans, which is 20%–30%. We need to address this phenomenon by enhancing the ability of artisans to directly reach buyers. Development Digital marketing can enable cooperative craftsmen to reap the potential benefits of direct consumer access (Ferreira et al., 2019). Realizing the potential for the development of the cooperative business, the service team from the Behavioral Marketing Research group increased knowledge and skills about digital marketing for craftsmen of household products made from natural fronds. Artisans need to understand the use of various social media such as Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube to promote their products to a wider market, including reaching consumers who are outside the city. In addition, craftsmen need to use business websites to inform the public of the quality of their products in detail in an effort to provide convenience in conducting business negotiations and payment transactions both to local and national consumers and in an effort to reach the potential of foreign markets (Setiawan et al., 2022). Through the website, artisans can also get input from consumers to improve services and improve the quality and design of products (Tung, 2012).

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

We must address the necessity of artisans adopting digital marketing gradually and sustainably to enhance product sales performance. We can implement activities for artisans that focus on problem identification, empowerment, and improvement. Problem identification

Received: 2023-06-09 Revised: 2023-06-21 Accepted: 2023-09-21 Published: 2023-12-31

can utilize a business model canvas to facilitate a comprehensive analysis of business challenges (Azizah, n.d.). Empowerment initiatives may involve workshops or training sessions that engage a majority of artisans, fostering awareness and capability to address issues. Experts can consistently guide a work team to execute improvements by implementing recommendations from problem identification and training topics.

The stages of implementing digital marketing in detail are as follows: Mapping problems with a business model canvas We carried out a two-week mapping of business problems in handicrafts in Murti Gading Village in early June 2023. Various business information is collected through direct contact with the leader of the craftsman group and direct survey of the service team in the field. The next step is the description of the problem through the analysis of the business model canvas, which seeks to pay attention to the interconnectedness of the 9 business elements depicted. Key partners The key partners of artisans are 1) collector farmers and traders of natural fronds from water hyacinth, pandan, and pineapple fiber 2) stores supplying raw materials: glue, dyes 3) suppliers of craft wood 4) suppliers of iron. Key activities in production are the creation of craft designs according to orders or the manufacture of products for sale stock. In addition, there are other key activities, namely the search for and transportation of natural ingredients and the delivery of orders to consumers. Value proposition The value of the products offered is the attractiveness of natural fibers that are environmentally friendly and the uniqueness of the design product. Consumer segment Product consumers are wholesalers who order goods to be sold to the local market (hotels and offices) and export markets. In addition, buyers who come directly to the craftsman to meet the needs of certain products. Customer relationships Pedagang contacts craftsmen to order products with special designs. Meanwhile, individual consumers come to their homes to see various handicraft options and buy products as desired .

Cost structure The cost component consists of the procurement of natural fronds (water hyacinth, bananas, pandan, and pineapple), the purchase of supporting raw materials (glue and dyeing agents), the salaries of natural frond processing employees, the salaries of assembler employees, and the salaries of product shippers. Key resources There are various important employees who support the product manufacturing process, which can be categorized into several types, namely natural frond processing employees, assembly employees, and product shipper employees. Revenue streams Most of the income received by artisans is the result of transactions on the sale of handicraft products from either payments from wholesalers or end consumers for order completion and purchases from direct consumers (10 percent of the revenue amount). Channels Direct orders from traders to artisans via WhatsApp WA or buyers come directly to artisans. Based on the mapping with the business model canvas above, it can be seen that two problems experienced by artisans who make natural fibers in Murtigading are

Received: 2023-06-09 Revised: 2023-06-21 Accepted: 2023-09-21 Published: 2023-12-31

1) Dependence on product sales to wholesalers Artisans are very dependent on wholesalers regarding the type and quantity of handicraft products. At first this pattern helped the development of handicraft sales. However, in the development of this business, this pattern greatly pressures craftsmen both in terms of price and type of product. 2) The limitation of sales media is only through direct contact via phone and WhatsApp. Artisans rely solely on direct ordering media via phone or WhatsApp. Although they have social media accounts such as Facebook and Instagram, they have not been used to promote products. In fact, the use of social media to display the attractiveness of products is very effective in reaching markets outside the region.

Table 1 presents the Business Model Canvas for Artisans who create products from

Natural Fibers		
Key Partner	Key activities	Value proposition
1) Farmers collecting & traders of natural fronds both from water hyacinth, pandan & pineapple fiber, 2) Raw material supplier shops: glue, dyes, 3) Craft wood suppliers, 4) Iron suppliers	1) making custom craft designs or making products for sales stock, 2) searching & transportation of natural materials as well as, 3) shipping orders to consumers	Natural fiber appeal of product design
Cost structure	Key resource	Revenue streams
Procurement of natural fronds (water hyacinth, bananas, pandanus & pineapples), purchase of supporting raw materials (glue, dyeing agents), salaries of natural frond processors, salaries of assemblers & salaries of product shippers	Natural frond processing employees, craft product assembly employees & product shippers	Payment from wholesalers for order fulfillment & purchase from direct consumers
Segments customers	Customers relationships	Channels
Wholesalers & Direct buyers	Traders provide designs for craftsmen to work on Buyers come to the house to choose existing products	Direct booking via WA Direct to the craftsman's house

Source: data processing

Received: 2023-06-09 Revised: 2023-06-21 Accepted: 2023-09-21 Published: 2023-12-31

The artisans received training on utilizing social media to promote their products. This training began with material on the importance of understanding the conditions and weaknesses experienced as well as awareness of the need for improvement in business management. The next material is about the importance of using social media to help expand market coverage and market response speed. A total of 20 members from the cooperative handicrafts participated seriously in the training session held at the Murtigading Cooperative Center. The training on the use of social media made participants aware that so far craftsmen have only used social media for daily activities. The benefits of social media have not been applied in supporting business promotion. Increasing the use of social media to support business does not require a large effort because social media can be used easily. The use of social media encourages an increase in sales because the reach of promotions becomes wider and promotional displays can be updated quickly. Therefore, they are asked to integrate menus in social media and prepare various product photos and videos to be promoted through Facebook and Instagram. There are several tips for social media craftsmen to get the attention of netizens: 1) Always respond to netizens' comments. 2) Display and update the appearance of product photos and videos in various ways. 3) Avoid Sara's comments and provoke conflicts. 4) Make variations of the display with various messages such as captions about spiritual advice, the spirit of life, or congratulations to the parties who celebrate.

Website design training to promote handicraft products, accompanied by a briefing to update the appearance of the website. The training with the topic "Make a Business Website Up to Air. In order for the trainees to share their experiences in developing their businesses, this training was also attended by several batik craftsmen. Several important materials related to digital marketing were presented in the training. Web experts in the workshop said the advantages of using a website are to increase the credibility or trust of potential consumers, make it easier to obtain information and promotional media, and also be easily accessible from various devices. Not only gaining knowledge of making a business website, participants are also invited to directly practice making business websites and online consultations until they become attractive websites. Meanwhile, the speaker in the shop explained the 4 criteria for a good-quality website, namely a responsive website, a design that is easy to use, fast website speed, and interesting and relevant content. As the third speaker in the workshop, he added that the business web complements the strategy of using social media in business promotion, such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and TikTok. By using the website, companies can enhance their credibility and improve the perception of their product quality. In addition, the business web is an effective means of expanding market areas and boosting sales turnover.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Cooperative craftsmen can maximize their use of Facebook and Instagram for product promotion by engaging in a variety of team-led activities. This process is not difficult because they already use social media—especially Facebook—to tell the status of their daily activities. They are advised to enrich the content of Facebook not only with daily activities but also with information about their craft business. In order to be able to deliver more intensive business promotions, they are advised to create a new account that specifically promotes their products. Meanwhile, the use of social media through Instagram has not been used intensively to share daily activities. Therefore, they are advised to create an Instagram account that can be used to promote their handicrafts. The service team also assisted the Murtigading Cooperative craftsmen to design their own website. The workshop participants practiced various skills to create a business website, which they completed in approximately two months. The service team accompanied the craftsmen to revise and update the content of the website for a year to adjust to the situation and various inputs from various parties. The website also describes each product sold clearly, including detailed product descriptions, selling prices, and product photos. In November 2023, several buyers from outside the region and abroad made contact. Through increasing the intensity of promotion through social media and improving business websites, it is proven that more and more buyers are looking at various artisan products. Although there are no buyers from abroad, the existence of a website shows its effectiveness in reaching potential consumers. Therefore, by improving the editorial of the website by accommodating two languages, it is hoped that it will be easier to convey promotions to buyers from abroad.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on digital marketing training activities applied to cooperative household product craftsmen, several conclusions were drawn that craftsmen have understood the need to master digital marketing through the use of social media, namely Facebook and Instagram. Craftsmen have understood and mastered website design to promote products. The use of digital marketing has increased the attention of consumers, both local and national, and foreign buyers, which is expected to increase the overall sales rate of artisans.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Received: 2023-06-09 Revised: 2023-06-21 Accepted: 2023-09-21 Published: 2023-12-31

REFERENCES

- Ferreira, J., Sousa, B. M., & Gonçalves, F. (2019). Encouraging the subsistence artisan entrepreneurship in handicraft and creative contexts. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 13(1/2), 64–83.
- Rejeb, A., Keogh, J. G., & Treiblmaier, H. (2020). How blockchain technology can benefit marketing: Six pending research areas. *Frontiers in Blockchain*, 3, 500660.
- Tung, F.-W. (2012). Weaving with Rush: Exploring Craft-Design Collaborations in Revitalizing a Local Craft. *International Journal of Design*, 6(3).